

**CHILD PROTECTION AND JUVENILE JUSTICE SYSTEM IN PAKISTAN: A
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ABSTRACT

the Research shows equivalences about the justice and child protection systems in Pakistan, the United States and the United Kingdom. It explores limited structures, social performs and legal systems to determine breaks, modifications and areas of development potential. This study shows how these countries balance the protection of children's rights and ensure that the juvenile justice system is fair and flexible. It also compares and differences Pakistan's juvenile justice and child protection systems with individuals of the United Kingdom and the United States. It also studies the organizational system, socio-cultural environment and legal framework in order to identify commonalities, identify differences and recognize possible areas for enhancement. Find out how these countries arrangement with challenges connected to protecting children's rights in their juvenile justice systems in a reasonable and supportive approach. By investigative these fundamentals, the research aims to reveal the strengths and weaknesses of each system and develop a deeper understanding of the above-mentioned juvenile justice and child care systems in our country.

1. INTRODUCTION.

Juvenile justice and protection of children's rights are two important legal and social issues of all nations. The understanding and development of this system has begun to attract more attention in recent years in countries such as Pakistan, the United States of America (USA) and the United Kingdom (UK), which focus especially on child and youth health. This comparative research main attentions to examine the constructions, practices and consequences of juvenile justice and child protection in Pakistan, the United States (USA) and the United Kingdom (UK). This study comparisons and differences methods to recognize comparisons, differences, rewards and shortcomings. The conclusions will provide direction for the development and application of various strategies. Moreover, the role of children in Pakistan's justice system, plus the permissible system, law implementation, medical services and management, will be examined in detail. Problems faced in the country include poverty, limited access to education and healthcare, child labor, human trafficking and cultural behaviours that fail to happen intercontinental child protection standards. Pakistan's juvenile justice system must be observed in detail, including its laws, implementation methods, rehabilitation and practices. The United Kingdom and the United States have established laws and institutions for the protection of children and juvenile justice. At the same time, these institutions were created through legal reform, judicial reform and cultural understanding. However, they have faced long-term problems such as conflict of justice, some groups in the justice system publishing publications aimed at children, and debates on the balance of punishment and rehabilitation.

1.1 BACKGROUND OF STUDY

While it is true that Pakistan is a developing nation, the country cannot accurately portray itself as such due to its low levels of education, wealth per capita, protection and development of children, elimination of child labour, and awareness of the importance of investing in its infrastructure and populace. The hope of a nation or civilization rests in its offspring, for it is they who will one day lead or change it. Children are increasingly seen as valuable resources for their country. Because of its significance, several national and international regulations are in place to safeguard children's rights. Through its national policy, the government of Pakistan has accepted its obligation to protect and care for children. In an effort to reduce inequality and provide social justice, the government should work to ensure that all children are treated fairly and have access to the same opportunities for growth and development. Unfortunately, in Pakistan, there is not enough attention paid to plants, child welfare, or implementation of policies that would help children develop

holistically. Most children in Pakistan do not have access to adequate care, protection, or significance during childhood despite constitutional ideas and promises of these things.

It is often said that a country's children are its most valuable resource. Every child has the right to a safe and happy childhood and the chance to mature into a productive adult. They have the right to meet or exceed societal standards for health and mental acuity. All kids need the same chances to grow and flourish while they're young. Children in every culture are expected to grow up to be respectful and responsible members of society. Children disobey established social and legal rules for a variety of reasons. The status and circumstances of children should be considered in light of the growing number of reports of their involvement in criminal activity

The following are some of the most fundamental examples of when it is necessary to ensure the safety of children:

- During the perinatal period, certain women experience mortality as a result of inadequate healthcare and limited finances.
- Numerous children experience either neglect or abuse from their family, relatives, school, or neighborhood. Consequently, the outcome leads to their demise.
- In competitive environments, there is a concerning occurrence of children resorting to suicide as a result of unmet desires and underperformance.
- The rising prevalence of automobiles has resulted in a corresponding increase in fatalities as a consequence of road accidents.
- Infant mortality rates that occur before they complete their first year of life can be linked to inadequate attention, care, and availability of basic resources like healthy food and medical care.
- Due to their involvement in illegal activities, they have been arrested.
- Low birth weight babies are delivered sometimes.
- Due to inadequate provision of appropriate resources, a significant number of children experience a range of health-related problems.

The growth of technology and the internet has introduced a variety of challenges for children, encompassing issues such as using sexting and cyber stalking. Simultaneously, the internet and other technological tools serve as platforms for information collection and sharing. In few instances, children have been compelled to engage in self-inflicted mortality as a result of being subjected to cyberbullying and online stalking. Cyberbullying has emerged as a prominent issue affecting youngsters in contemporary society. There are a vast

number of websites that offer explicit and sexually-oriented content without being subject to legal limitations. The accessibility of pornography to minors is facilitated by online platforms.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This study relies on a good range of sources, and a couple of words should therefore be said about how they're applied. The common denominator for the material that has been examined is that it relates to child conflict with law. Universal and regional human rights treaties that in some way address children, the jurisprudence of these instruments, policy documents, relevant Acts, action plans, reports from intergovernmental agencies and nongovernmental organizations, legal doctrine and interviews with academics are all important sources. The documentation of the work of the Committee on the protection of Child from – state party reports, summary records from the sessions where the state party reports are discussed, the Committee 's concluding observations, and any additional information such as reports from non-governmental organization is of fundamental importance for this analysis.

The comparative study of child protection and the juvenile justice system in Pakistan with the U.K. and the U.S.A. involves analysing various aspects of these systems. The juvenile justice system in the U.S.A. faces challenges in providing mental health services to detained youth with psychiatric disorders (Teplin et al., 2002). On the other hand, the system in Pakistan has been criticized for the delay and denial of justice (Bilal & Khokhar, 2021). The juvenile justice system's guiding principles have always been to safeguard the child's best interests, as opposed to the adult criminal justice system's emphasis on punishment or public safety (Felker-Kantor, 2016).

Regarding the juvenile justice system's function, it is critical to focus on addressing the needs of young people with mental health illnesses by working in conjunction with the larger community (Underwood & Washington, 2016). Furthermore, the system ought to place a focus on providing adolescents in legal trouble with protection, treatment, rehabilitation, rearrangement, and reintegration (Sharma, 2021). Furthermore, by contribution reasonable wraparound services, the system needs to concentrate on lowering recidivism rates among young offenders (Pullmann et al., 2006). Comparison systems internationally, the America juvenile justice system is in a quandary, whereas the China

juvenile justice system has moved toward responsibility and punitiveness (Zhang & He, 2018).

In general, factors like mental health services, delays in the administration of justice, rehabilitation philosophies, community engagement, and recidivism should be taken into account when comparing Pakistan's juvenile justice system to those in the United Kingdom and the United States of America.

Overall, the study of child protection and the juvenile justice system in Pakistan compared to the U.K. and the U.S.A. should consider aspects such as mental health services, delays in justice delivery, rehabilitation philosophies, community collaboration, recidivism reduction, international variations in juvenile justice approaches, and the importance of tailored services for specific youth populations.

John Sutton, *Stubborn Children: Controlling Delinquency in the United States*

It's good that John Sutton writes about how reforms in the U.S. have changed over time to try to keep kids in line. He focuses on a number of important changes, from Puritan tactics for keeping kids in line in colonial times to the refuge and reformatory movements of the 1800s, to the court and, more recently, the movement for deinstitutionalization. John Sutton, in his book *Stubborn Children: Controlling Delinquency in the United States*, gives a compelling account of the development of reforms to curb juvenile delinquency in the United States. He examines a chain of seminal reforms, beginning with colonial Puritan methods of kid control and progressing through the nineteenth-century refuge and reformatory movements, the court system, and the current deinstitutionalization movement.

Shook, Jeffrey J, *Contesting Childhood in the US Justice System:*

The Transfer of Juveniles to Adult Criminal Court The line between juvenile and criminal justice in the United States has been blurred by recent legislation. Youth who were once classified as juveniles are increasingly being labelled "adults" and tried as such in the legal system. The essay opens with a discussion of recent shifts in how juveniles are handed over to the legal system. The author delves into the significance of these shifts in social and political discourses for constructions of childhood and the contestation of childhood they reflect. The study finishes with a theoretical framework for dissecting and reformulating juvenile trials.

Juvenile Justice: A Guide to Theory, Policy, and Practice

This essential text by Stephen Cox, Jennifer Allen, and Robert Hanser provides a concise and current overview of the juvenile justice system, guiding students through topics like the system's history, crime measurement, theories of crime causation, the juvenile justice process, community-based sanctions, treatment and rehabilitation, gangs, and international youth crime. This updated edition of *Juvenile Justice: A Guide to Theory, Policy, and Practice* provides readers with fresh examples and updated visuals to help them grasp the complex links between theory, policy, and practice in the field of juvenile justice.

Juvenile Delinquency, Theory, Practice and Law, Larry J. Siegel, Brandon C. Welse
JUVENILE DELINQUENCY: THEORY, PRACTICE, AND LAW Timely coverage of theory, policy, and the most recent research is what you'll find in *Juvenile Delinquency, Theory, Practice, and Law* by Larry J. Siegel and Brandon C. Welse. This book, lauded for its fair treatment of the issues it addresses and the compelling literary style adopted by its writers, will help readers gain insight into the nature, causes, and contemporary approaches to reducing and ultimately eliminating juvenile delinquency.

Juvenile Sexual Offending, causes, consequences and correction, Gail Ryan, Tom Leversee, Sandy Lane.

It offers a research-based, outcome-focused method for evaluating and caring for this challenging group of people. The paper, written by top researchers in the area, marks major advances in our understanding of how the brain develops. Comprehensive and actionable instructions for estimating the possibility of future offences, as well as an introduction to the risk assessment methodology, are provided.

An introduction to child protection legislation in the UK

This information sheet serves as an introduction to some of the most important laws in the United Kingdom that were enacted to safeguard children and teenagers. These additional references offer further insights into child protection policies, global perspectives on juvenile justice systems, challenges in implementing child protection laws, rehabilitation programs for juvenile offenders, and comparative analyses of legal frameworks for child protection in Pakistan, the United Kingdom (UK) and the United State of America (USA)

3. SIGNIFICANCE/JUSTIFICATION OF STUDY:

Chapter "Genesis and Antecedents of Juvenile Justice" of this paper provides a historical account of the development and evolution of juvenile justice systems across the globe. The article proceeds to explicate the provenance of the terms "juvenile" and "delinquents" before delving into the history and foundation of juvenile courts, as well as their jurisdiction. A distinction between the "infant" and the "adult" in accordance with Blackstone's commentaries is also discussed. This could be interpreted as the origin of juvenile justice in the contemporary sense. Children who committed the criminal offence after reaching the age of 14 were subject to the same penalties as an adult, whereas a child who was younger than seven years old was deemed incapable of developing the requisite criminal intent. It has been suggested that quasi-judicial tribunals be established in light of the ineffectiveness of adult criminal courts in dealing with juvenile offenders. Over time, these tribunals gave rise to executive and procedural guidelines, thereby establishing an institutionalized mechanism to influence the delinquents. The comprehensive evolution of legislation pertaining to the juvenile system in Pakistan and the origins of separate treatment for juveniles are discussed. It provides an in-depth historical account of the laws that lead to the establishment of fashionable legal mechanisms in the United States, the United Kingdom, and Pakistan.

The following chapter of the thesis examines the theory and causes of juvenile delinquency as deviant child behavior that is influenced by societal norms, specifically those established by older generations, and conflicts of values resulting from generational differences. The perception and analysis of juvenile delinquency by penologists is another subject of consideration. Furthermore, it examines the various types, theories, and origins of juvenile delinquency. The two personality types of delinquents are extroverts and introverts. The text highlights a multitude of theories that have been put forth thus far regarding delinquent behavior and argues that no single theory satisfactorily explains its origins. Rather, it posits that a complex interplay of numerous factors contributes to the development of such antisocial conduct. A comprehensive examination of every biological, sociological, and psychological theory has been completed within the chapter.

In the chapter entitled Juvenile Justice System in U.K. & U.S., the current legislative practices and judicial systems of the United Kingdom and the United States of America pertaining to juvenile justice are examined in depth. Using case laws, the evolution of the

mechanism in the United States has been illustrated. The chapter provides an analysis of the current systems in both nations and lists their advantages and disadvantages.

The chapter titled "Constitutional and Legal Mechanism for Child Protection in Pakistan" provides an in-depth analysis of the mechanism that is currently in place within our nation. Children are granted certain privileges as citizens of Pakistan under the constitution. In recognition of their unique status, the government has implemented specific legislation. The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child states that the constitution, which was adopted in 1950, protects the majority of rights regarded as fundamental rights and directive principles of state policy. Numerous individuals and public interest organizations have petitioned the highest court for the restoration of fundamental rights, including those of children, over the years. Article 15(3) permits the enactment of special legislation pertaining to minors. The article unequivocally declares that "nothing in this article shall prevent the State from making any special provision."

The Pakistani Constitution's articles bestow authority and impose responsibilities on the State to guarantee the fulfilment of every child's need and the complete protection of their fundamental rights. In order to provide a clearer picture of the juvenile justice system in the country, the provisions of the Juvenile Justice Act of 2018 have been detailed. It provides comprehensive information regarding the mechanism, such as the Juvenile Justice Board, age determination, juvenile justice fund, and child rehabilitation, among others. The chapter titled "Judicial Trends in Pakistan and Juvenile Justice" discusses a multitude of developments that have been subsequently addressed through legislative measures and court decisions within the Juvenile Justice System of Pakistan.

The following are examples of international instruments:

- Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), 1948;
- The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, (ICCPR),1966;
- International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR),1966;
- Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), 1979;
- Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC), 1990;
- Convention against Torture (CAT), 1984;

- Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD), 2006; and
- Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination (CERD), 1965.

National Instruments are as such:

- Juvenile Justice System Ordinance, 2000.
- Juvenile Justice System Act, 2018 (It has repealed JJSO, 2000).
- Qanoon-e-Shahadat Order, 1984; •The Hudood Laws, 1979.
- Punjab Borstal Act, 1926; •Punjab Youthful Offenders Act, 1983.
- Sindh Borstal School Act, 1955; •Sindh Children Act 1955.
- The Baluchistan Borstal Institution Act, 2014.
- Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Child Protection and Welfare Act, 2010;
- Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Borstal Institution Act (KPBIA), 2012.
- Punjab Destitute and Neglected Children Act (PDNCA), 2004.

4. OBJECTIVES OF STUDY/RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Following are objectives of this study:

- To give a full account of how the juvenile justice system has changed over time around the world; to talk about how juvenile courts have changed over time as well as how administrative and judicial rules and laws have changed.
- To help explain the idea behind, and the motives that encourage for juvenile crime
- To talk about different laws enacted by the Pakistani government, like the Juvenile Justice Act, as well as important UN principles and laws made by the UK and USA governments and its implementation progress
- To talk about the part that non-governmental organisations, professional groups, the media, schools, kids, and other people in civil society played in the process in protection of children.

- To suggest a plan for a comprehensive approach to implementation that makes the best use of resources and efforts, ensures responsibility and openness in operations, and makes sure that children are involved in the parts of society that matter and to make sure that preventative reactions are based on effective ways to stop problems and fix them.

5. METHODOLOGY OF THE RESEARCH WORK

The present study will undertake a doctrinal study with a specific emphasis on the subject matter of Child Protection and the Juvenile Justice System. The primary objective of this research, however, is to ascertain and elucidate the significance of the Juvenile Justice Act in safeguarding the rights of children, and to examine the present circumstances pertaining to children in Pakistan. The aim of this study is to identify potential justifications for the current disparity observed between verbal assertions and actual outcomes. The analysis of numerous literary works, academic journals, periodicals, court records, and other primary and secondary sources of data forms the foundation of the study.

6. CONCLUSION:

In summary, this comparative analysis sheds light on juvenile justice and child protection issues in Pakistan, the United States of America (USA) and the United Kingdom (UK) We identify each system's comparisons and differences, as well as its assets and weaknesses, by investigative its strategies, update rules, practices, and consequences. While Pakistan has finished efforts to determination issues in the execution of child law and protection of children's rights, mostly in the legal outline, organizational procedures and leadership, significant differences continue. It is clear that Pakistan requirements comprehensive improvements to improve juvenile justice and child protection, meeting on aligning the law with global standards, increasing access to justice, and strengthening rehabilitation and programs for the combination of young offenders into society. On the other hand, although justice for children and the protection of children have enhanced in the United States (USA) and the United Kingdom (UK), both Counties still face long-term problems such as justice conflicts and concerns about the action of young offenders. But these countries still benefit from flexible laws, deterrence strategies and recovery events that can serve as reproductions for progress in other parts. The Historical events that effect each country's method to juvenile justice and child protection. He highlighted the need for consistent assessment, communication and collaboration to reply to developing issues and certify that all children

have rights and well-being. Policymakers, experts, and staff should consider the results of this study as they seek to develop evidence-based strategies that prioritize children's interests.

Overall, this comparative research underlines the importance of understanding the cultural, societal, and historical contexts that shape each country's approach to child protection and juvenile justice. It emphasizes the need for continuous evaluation, dialogue, and collaboration to address the evolving challenges and ensure the rights and well-being of all children are upheld. Moving forward, it is imperative for policymakers, practitioners, and advocates to heed the findings of this research and work towards implementing evidence-based reforms that prioritize the best interests of children.

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